

Pilot-Scale CO₂ capture in a cement plant with CESAR1: Emission control with acid wash and absorber intercooling

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates how to reduce emissions from degradation byproducts. A pilot scale unit is used to capture CO₂ from cement flue gas, using a AMP/PZ solvent blend, commonly known as the CESAR1 solvent. To reduce emissions, we implemented a wash tower. The wash tower was operated both with a single and double bed water wash and with an acid wash. Another emission control strategy was operating the capture process with intercooling on the absorber column. We used ammonia emissions as a key indicator of solvent degradation.

When implementing a wash tower, equipped with an acid wash section, a 92.4% reduction in amine degradation byproducts in the gas could be achieved. Several compounds reached non-detectable levels, indicating a substantial decrease in degradation products escaping the system.

Introducing a double water wash bed reduced ammonia levels but was insufficient to remove it altogether, highlighting the temperature dependency of ammonia solubility and the limited effectiveness of water in thermally driven systems.

Additionally, the study revealed that absorber intercooling effectively minimized degradation byproducts by controlling the solvent temperature, significantly influencing the amount of degradation products emitted.

These findings suggest that integrating acid washing with intercooling can significantly improve amine-based carbon capture systems' efficiency, durability, and environmental performance.

1. Introduction

The results of human activity in climate change are evident through the alteration of various weather patterns and climatic extremes across the globe [1], and its impact needs to be abated. Carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) technologies are promising candidates for reducing carbon emissions, mitigating climate change, and striving for climate neutrality in the coming decades.

Amine-based chemical absorption is the most mature carbon capture technology, with first-generation plants currently implemented on a technical scale [2]. Within amine capture, monoethanolamine (MEA) is the most studied solvent. MEA is considered a benchmark solvent in

terms of energy intensity [3,4] due to its fast kinetics at CO₂ absorption [5], as well as its widespread use and relatively well-understood performance. However, conventional carbon capture using MEA has a high energy consumption for solvent regeneration (3.6–3.8 GJ/ton of CO₂ [6,7]), due to a higher demand of reboiler duty. Furthermore, MEA is highly corrosive to process equipment and is susceptible to degradation [8,9].

To optimize CO₂ capture, alternative solvents are being studied and developed. These solvents aim to improve reaction kinetics, reduce energy requirements, minimize degradation and improve reclaimability. One such solvent is the CESAR1 solvent, an aqueous solution of 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP), promoted with piperazine (PZ). While

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AMP has a higher absorption capacity, requires less energy for regeneration, and is less prone to degradation [10–12], it suffers from slow reaction kinetics. That is solved with the use of PZ. A small amount of PZ promotes the reaction speed of CO₂ with AMP. [13]. Therefore, the CESAR1 solvent is superior to MEA in terms of energy required for regeneration.

Although, CESAR1's susceptibility towards degradation remains a concern [14–16], Moser et al. [17] found that MEA presents a non-linear self-acceleration degradation behavior, whereas CESAR1 experiences a slower, linear degradation rate. Despite this, certain compounds, such as ammonia, small organic acids, and volatile organic compounds, are expected to form in all amine solvents, including AMP/PZ blends [18].

There are two main types of amine degradation. Amine solutions degrade due to the presence of O₂ in the inlet gas, commonly known as oxidative degradation [19], or thermal degradation due to the high operational temperatures of the desorption process [20]. Some byproducts of amine degradation are highly volatile and can be environmentally hazardous if emitted with the depleted gas to the atmosphere [21,22]. Furthermore, the solvent amines can also be volatile, contributing to potential emissions.

In the case of CESAR1, Morlando et al. [18], reports that AMP is found to be more volatile than MEA, whereas PZ is less volatile than both [23–26]. A key concern regarding CESAR1 solvent emissions is that PZ, being a secondary amine, can readily undergo nitrosation. As a result of oxidative degradation or exposure to NO₂ deriving from the flue gas, it can form nitrosamines, which are known to be carcinogenic. The primary nitrosamine derived from PZ is N-nitrosopiperazine (MNPZ) with some formation of dinitrosopiperazine (DNPZ) also occurring. MNPZ has lower volatility compared to the primary MEA-derived nitrosamine, N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA), which reduces the likelihood of it escaping the carbon capture system [18].

Most amine degradation byproducts are water-soluble. However, studies have shown a limited impact on removing gas emissions using water. In the order of 20% amine degradation products, can be removed when using water [27]. Several methods have been developed for removal of impurities following a CO₂ capture plant, including single stage water wash and multistage water wash [28,29]. Moser et al. [30] found that utilizing a dry bed at the top of the absorber column can significantly reduce amine emissions. Additionally, Liu et al. [31] found that altering the plants operational parameters (solvent-to-gas-ratio, lean solvent loading, absorber temperature profile) influences the emission levels.

One of the more promising developing methods is the packed-bed acid scrubbing method, reaching impurity removal efficiencies of up to 90% [32]. Studies have proven the effectiveness of implementing acid as an absorbent to treat degradation byproducts [27,32–37], with only a few specializing in packed-bed acid-scrubbing towers [29,31,34,35]. However, currently, there are limited studies on the effectiveness of an acid wash in treating CESAR1 emissions from cement flue gas.

In this work, we investigate various ways to control degradation emissions from a CO₂ capture plant receiving flue gas from a cement plant, using the CESAR1 solvent. The effectiveness of implementing an acid wash section in reducing CESAR1 solvent degradation product contents in the treated gas stream is evaluated. Furthermore, we investigate the synergistic effects of an absorber intercooler on minimizing these compounds. The study utilized a packed-bed acid scrubbing tower to treat the gas stream, focusing on various operational parameters. The acid used was 0.1 M sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄). The pilot operation was shifted from a base case configuration to an intercooler (IC) setup to assess its impact on emissions and degradation product buildup. The implementation of the acid wash showed a significant reduction in amine degradation products, with some reaching non-detectable levels. Additionally, the intercooler configuration proved effective in reducing the production of these byproducts, indicating a promising approach for enhancing solvent longevity.

These findings suggest that integrating an acid bed while utilizing

the intercooler can mitigate degradation in amine-based solvents, thereby improving the efficiency and longevity of a thermal carbon capture plant.

2. Experimental setup and Methodology

We use a mobile carbon capture unit (Mobile Test Unit, MTU) capable of capturing up to 1 ton of CO₂ per day. In the past, the unit has been used for biogas upgrading by Jørsboe et al. [38,39] and by Vinjarapu et al. [40] and Neerup et al. [9] for post-combustion carbon capture at a waste-to-energy facility.

The pilot is constructed in four process skids, as shown in Fig. 1a. The upper two skids are the four columns of the unit: the absorber and the desorber (skid D, Fig. 1a), the wash tower, and an additional column used for advanced configurations (skid C). The lower two skids are the remaining process equipment, such as the blower, filters, heat exchangers, transmitters, etc.

The pilot allows for several advanced process configurations, such as absorber intercooling, lean vapor recompression (LVC), rich recycle split feed, and more. Fig. 1b shows the MTU campaigning at Aalborg Portland A/S, Denmark.

2.1. Overview of pilot plant

The overview of the pilot unit is shown in Fig. 2 Indicated by a simplified process flow diagram of the pilot plant. The plant is designed to accommodate several advanced process configurations. It is equipped with traditional absorber and stripper columns. In addition, the unit also has:

- 1) an activated carbon filter for gas pre-treatment,
- 2) a wash tower with a waterbed, dry bed, an acid loop, and a polishing section,
- 3) a compressor for various heat pump tests.
- 4) an additional tower that is used for advanced configurations. Not shown in Fig. 2.

While not all configurations shown in Fig. 2 are addressed in this study, their inclusion showcases the plant's broad adaptability and potential for future use.

All columns are made of 316 stainless steel. The absorber is 19.34 m tall and packed with Flexiring (Flex) 5/8 in. random. The absorber consists of three packing sections: the bottom two sections are 5.33 m tall and the third top section is 4.35 m. The stripper is 17.54 m tall, packed with Flexiring (Flex) 5/8 in. random packing, and it consists of four packing sections, with the top three sections measuring 3.5 m in height and the bottom section measuring 3.4 m. The wash tower is 13.4 m tall, packed with 8.69 m of Kock-Glitsch Flexiring (KGF) 5/8 in. random packing. The wash tower comprises six sections, five packed beds, and a demister. The bottom section has a height of 1.09 m, while the remaining four packed beds measure 1.9 m of packing. The demister at the top of the column has a height of 0.3 m. The design details of the columns are summarized in Table 1.

2.2. Wash tower characteristics

2.2.1. Wash beds

The wash tower removes harmful environmental emissions from the cleaned flue gas. The wash tower has six packed bed sections and is divided into three different overall sections. In the bottom, the water wash is located, which consists of two packed bed sections. In the middle is an acid wash section with one packed bed. Lastly, at the top is a polishing section with one packed bed, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

The polishing section serves as the final purification stage, utilizing a circulating water loop, before the gas is returned to the kiln stack. However, this section was not in operation during this study.

Fig. 1. a) 3d model of the capture plant (adapted from vinjarapu et al.[40]). b) The MTU campaigning in Aalborg Portland A/S, Denmark.

The water wash has a crucial role in the carbon capture unit by maintaining the plant's water balance. That is achieved by cooling the gas that exits the absorber, maintaining the outlet temperature closely aligned with the inlet throughout the operation. Additionally, the water wash has a role in partially removing amine degradation products.

The wash tower operates near ambient conditions, with negligible heat loss since its primary function is to maintain water balance.

2.2.2. Acid wash beds

The acid wash is placed above the water wash section, as shown in Fig. 2. The acid wash has a loop of its own that is equipped with a circulation pump. Unlike the water wash, the acid loop is a contained system with no active liquid removal, with any additions originating solely from possible moisture in the incoming gas. Possible condensed water is calculated to minimal over days of operation. The acid loop is equipped with a pH probe, which allows for continuous monitoring of the acid and ensures immediate detection of any pH variations.

The acid section was installed to reduce the amount of degradation products that escape the plant after the absorber. Most amine degradation products are higher pH compounds [41,42], which are neutralized by an acid. After the initial treatment in the water wash section, the gas is scrubbed with acid in the acid wash section. The acid wash is one of the number of configurations that the plant allows for. When not tested, the acid is stored in a dedicated sump, to prevent neutralization, as shown in Fig. 2. The vessel has a capacity of 29 L, excluding the volume of liquid in the circulation pipes.

When the unit was first constructed, no regulations were in place for amine degradation emissions. The wash tower was installed to test the effect of acid scrubbing on reducing the emissions. As of May 2023, no

restrictions have been imposed on amine related emissions from carbon capture plants stacks. However, the Danish Environmental Protection Agency has published emission regulation regarding the total maximum contribution regulation regarding the total maximum contribution level for carbon capture technologies. These regulations are commonly known as 'C-values'. The evaluation proposes a limitation of ground-level concentrations to 0.07 mg/m³, 0.07 mg/m³ and 0.001 mg/m³ for MEA, AMP and PZ, respectively [42].

2.3. Gas flow through the plant

The pilot plant received flue gas from a cement stack. The flue gas composition contained a variety of impurities, depending primarily on the fuel used in the kiln.

Upstream of the MTU, the flue gas passes through a cooler, where it is cooled to 30–50 °C. The condensate is collected and pumped to a nearby slurry tank in relation to cement production.

As illustrated in Fig. 3, the cooled flue gas enters the system and goes through a knock-out drum to separate the liquid from the gas phase and remove possible condensation in the inlet gas. Following is an activated carbon filter filled with activated carbon. The filter is designed to remove hydrogen chloride (HCl) from the flue gas to prevent the piping and the equipment from corroding. The pressure loss of the filter ranged from 10 to 100 mbarg.

Downstream of the knock-out drum and the activated carbon filter is the blower, see Fig. 3. The blower allows for a maximum airflow of 190 m³/h. The blower receives gas, saturated with water, and delivers it to the absorber column. Here it is contacted with the solvent, circulating through the system. CO₂ is absorbed in the solvent, and the CO₂ rich

Fig. 2. Process flow diagram of the pilot plant, including relevant advanced configurations for this study.

Table 1
Summary of the design data of the pilot columns.

Parameters	Absorber	Stripper	Wash tower
Height	19.34 m	17.54 m	13.4 m
Diameter	0.217 m	0.217 m	0.215 m
Volume	778 L	632 L	680 L
Packing Height	15 m	13.9 m	8.69 m
Packing material	Flex 5/8" random	Flex 5/8" random	KGF 5/8" random
Type storage vessel	Sump	Flash vessel	Sump
Volume storage vessel	120 L	120 L	34.2 L
Polishing section Height	0.5 m	0.5 m	0.3 m
Polishing material	Mellapak 250Y structured	Mellapak plus 250Y	

solvent stream goes through the main heat exchanger of the system and then enters the stripper column where it is heated up, and the CO₂ is desorbed. The CO₂ rich gas stream goes through a condenser to recover the water. The collected water is returned to the system, maintaining the unit's water balance.

The depleted gas stream exits the absorber and enters the wash tower from the bottom of the column. The gas goes through the water wash section to capture the condensate and return it to the system. Lastly, the

gas enters the acid wash (Fig. 3) and the polishing section before it exits the wash tower.

2.4. Campaign outline

The MTU was installed at Aalborg Portland in October 2022. The plant operated from January 2023 to September 2023. During the operational period, the plant reached almost 200 steady states and operated for 3900 h [43].

Multiple advanced process configurations of the plant were tested during this campaign. The aim was to test the effect of each on the solvent's loading, the plant's performance, and the reduction of the specific reboiler duty. Intercooler was implemented for a significant time of the campaign, yielding approximately 40 steady states.

2.5. Intercooling configuration

The intercooling configuration enhances CO₂ absorption by cooling down the solvent. The colder the liquid, the higher the gas solubility. To implement the intercooler configuration, an additional heat exchanger and a pump are needed, and piping is installed to draw fluid from the absorber [44]. The solvent is drawn from the bottom of the packed bed in the absorber. From here, it is cooled down by passing through the heat exchanger before being returned to the column, as shown in Fig. 2. In

Table 2
FTIR measurement ranges of analysis method for post-combustion gas.

Component	Unit	Range 1	Range 2	Range 3
CO ₂	vol%	0–20	–	–
H ₂ O	vol%	0–30	0–40	–
CO	mg/m ³	0–75	0–300	0–2000
NO	mg/m ³	0–80	0–200	0–600
NO ₂	mg/m ³	0–50	0–200	0–500
N ₂ O	mg/m ³	0–50	0–100	–
SO ₂	mg/m ³	0–75	0–300	0–1275
NH ₃	mg/m ³	0–15	0–50	–
HCl	mg/m ³	0–15	0–100	0–1000

for gas analysis using heated pipes and vacuum pumps.

Each measurement's detection limit was determined based on a standard performance check, including 60 min of sampling, normal suction levels, and accredited analysis. Methods that measure multiple parameters, like trace metals, may have different detection limits for each species, with the lowest value being reported. The detection limit was calculated as the average of repeated blank measurements plus three times the standard deviation of those blanks.

Uncertainty was based on measurements taken at sampling sites that meet the requirements of EN 15259 for grid measurements. For this work, uncertainty was presented as a percentage of the measured value (the relative standard deviation) or as an absolute value. The uncertainty reflects the typically achievable precision at average concentrations well above the detection limit.

Monitor drift, the unintended gradual change in the performance or calibration of a measurement over time, is controlled daily by zero- and span-readings before and after the measurements. If the drift is larger than 5%, the sample is discarded. All monitor results are corrected for drift, and the result from the drift control is shown in the overview. All monitors and sampling equipment are tested for leaks according to the relevant standards. The sample is discarded if the leak is larger than the allowed value.

2.9.2.1. Analytical methods and measurement parameters for flue gas components. In a dry partial flow of flue gas, free of particles, the concentrations for various components are determined using specific analytical methods. Table 3 showcases the limit of detection, uncertainty, the methods employed, and references for measuring CO₂, O₂, CO, NO_x (NO, NO₂, N₂O), and total volatile organic carbon concentration (TVOC).

2.9.2.2. Sampling and measurement of HCl, SO₂, NH₃, and formaldehyde. For components like HCl, SO₂, NH₃, and formaldehyde, the partial flow from each sample stream is aspirated through a filter followed in series by two impingers made of borosilicate glass with a frit. Each component has a different liquid matrix used to absorb the chemical component. The limit of detection, the uncertainty, and the reference/standard used to analyze each component are shown in Table 4.

However, it is possible that during the sampling process, aerosols

Table 3
Analytical methods and standards for the main components as provided by FORCE Technologies.

Component	Unit	Range	Limit of Detection	Uncertainty	Method	Reference/Standard
CO ₂	vol %	0–20 (d)	0.13001	6% of measurement value	Nondispersive infrared (NDIR) monitor	CEN/TS 17405: 2020
O ₂	vol %	0–25 (d)	0.2094	6% of measurement value	Para-magnetic pilot cell	EN 14789: 2017
CO	ppm	0–1000 (d)	8.016	6% of measurement value	Nondispersive infrared (NDIR) monitor	EN 15058: 2017
NO _x	ppm	0–100000 (d)	2.156	10% of the measurement value	Chemiluminescence monitor with a built-in converter	EN 14792: 2017
TVOC	ppm	0–30000C (w)	0.08	10% of measurement value	FID monitor calibrated with propane or methane	EN 12619: 2013

(d) indicates dry conditions, (w) indicates wet conditions.

Table 4
Gas analysis is done using analytical methods and impingers.

Component	Liquid matrix	Unit	Limit of Detection	Uncertainty	Reference/Standard
HCl	100 ml of deionized water	mg/m ³ (s, d)	0.2	12% of the measurement value	EN 1911: 2010
SO ₂	100 ml liquid solution (0.3% H ₂ O ₂)	mg/m ³ (s, d)	0.2	12% of the measurement value	EN 14791: 2017
NH ₃	100 ml liquid solution (0.05 M H ₂ SO ₄)	mg/m ³ (s, d)	0.2	12% of the measurement value	ISO EN 21877: 2019
Formaldehyde	50–100 ml DNPH in sulphuric solution	mg/m ³ (s, d)	0.002	20% of the measurement value	VDI 3862, blatt 2

may have escaped the system, potentially leading to elevated readings for some emissions. Additionally, due to the method of analysis for SO₂, monitoring SO₃ was not feasible.

2.9.2.3. Amines, amine degradation products, and amides. The partial flow from the sample stream is drawn through a train of three impingers made of borosilicate glass with frit. The first impinger is left empty to collect condensate, while the next two contain around 100 ml of 0.1 M sulphamic acid in ultra-high-quality (UHQ) water. The impingers are kept in an ice bath during sampling to maintain a cool temperature. After each sample is taken, the probe and tubing are rinsed with an absorbent liquid to collect additional samples from the potential condensation in the pipes.

All sample fractions, including the rinsing liquid, condensate, and impingers, are combined into a single sample and analyzed by the SINTEF Department of Mass Spectrometry in Norway.

As of November 2023, no standard or reference has been established for the analysis of amine-related compounds in gas streams. The analysis of these compounds follows a method developed by Fraboulet et al. [45].

The uncertainties of the amine measurements are estimated to be 12% of the measured value, corresponding to a 95% confidence interval. When measured values approach the limit of quantification, the uncertainty may increase. Additionally, the absorption efficiency of the impingers has been tested and is found to exceed the 95% criterion.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Influence of external parameters

During the campaign, the MTU was positioned outdoors near the stack (Fig. 5). The bottom skirts were sheltered from the elements such as snow and rain, using a temporary cover tent. However, despite the

Fig. 5. MTU campaigning in Aalborg Portland. Highlighted in green are the wash and the MVR tower, and highlighted in red are the absorber and desorber. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

insulation, the columns were still affected by changing weather conditions (Fig. 6).

The plant has two temperature probes equipped on the wash tower (Ext(W), Fig. 6) and the absorber column (Ext(A), Fig. 6) to monitor outside temperatures. The temperature profiles of the absorber and the wash tower during operation are shown in Fig. 6. The average

operational temperatures for the columns were calculated for the months of operation, excluding intercooling configuration temperatures. The absorber had a minimum average operational temperature of 49.6 °C and a maximum of 70.9 °C, while the wash tower had a range of 18.6 °C to 34.7 °C.

The temperature change in the absorber and extension of the wash

Fig. 6. Average temperatures of the packed beds of the columns for all months of operation excluding intercooler.

tower can have an impact on emissions [46–49]. The studies indicate that increasing the absorber temperature from 40 °C may reduce amine aerosol emissions. Additionally, Mertens et al. [50] examined the impact of water wash temperature on ammonia emission levels and the influence of the water temperature on removing degradation compounds. They discovered that reducing the water temperature from 50 °C to 35 °C, temporarily reduced emissions levels, until the system reached equilibrium.

Overall, the operational temperatures of the absorber and wash tower are essential for effective emissions control and should be considered during plant operation. Adjustments to the temperature profiles of these columns can significantly impact both emissions and the degradation of compounds.

3.2. Inlet gas composition

3.2.1. Impact of fuel changes on flue gas composition

The flue gas composition can change depending on the kind of clinker being produced and the selected fuels used. The impact of a fuel change in the kiln on flue gas composition was measured using FTIR at the pilot plant inlet (GS1, Fig. 4). At around 14:15, Aalborg Portland adjusted the kiln fuel, increasing the use of alternative fuels (waste) while reducing the coal feed. The effect of this adjustment is observed in Fig. 7 at 14:45, as indicated by the green line. It takes roughly 30 min for changes in the kiln fuel to be reflected in the flue gas emissions.

Following the fuel change, there was a noticeable shift in the flue gas composition, as shown in Fig. 7. The CO levels decreased from approximately 500 to approximately 180 ppm. In the meantime, the NO level increased from approximately 120 to approximately 230 ppm. The

CO₂ percentage decreased from approximately 22 to 20%. This means the addition of alternative fuels changed the flue gas composition significantly.

From 15:10 until 15:30 (Fig. 7), there was a minor disturbance in the alternative fuel feed, resulting in an increase in the coal feed to the kiln and a decrease in alternative fuel. A temporary blockage of the feeder caused the disturbance. After 15:30, the kiln still received coal at lower levels, which decreased further in the following hours. This disturbance is reflected in the measurements, as shown in Fig. 7 by the black line. The CO levels increased from approximately 180 to 250 ppm, and the NO decreased from approximately 230 to 160 ppm. This demonstrates once again that the addition of alternative fuels into the kiln significantly impacts the composition of flue gas.

These measurements indicate how influential the kiln fuel is to the flue gas composition. Variations in the kiln fuel feed result in observable changes in the stack impurity levels. This underscores the importance of monitoring kiln fuel feed, as specific flue gas impurities, e.g. O₂, NO_x, and SO₂, can lead to solvent degradation, and thus amine degradation emissions, by reacting with the amine solvent [9,51–54]. Significant changes in impurity levels should be carefully observed as to secure solvent longevity.

3.2.2. Comparison of CO₂ measurements

To evaluate the precision of CO₂ measurements, the relative offset between the CO₂ measured at the stack, and the CO₂ that is measured at the pilot was calculated by comparing the two values using values collected over a period of 6 days.

In this work, the coefficient of variation (CV) is used as a statistic value that represents the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean,

Fig. 7. Flue gas composition live measurements during a kiln fuel change on 30/05/2023, as measured with FTIR by FORCE Technologies.

expressed as a percentage. A lower CV indicates less variability among data points, while a higher CV suggests greater variability. In this context, the CV helps assess the accuracy of CO₂ measurements at the pilot compared to those at the stack.

It is found that there is a difference between the mole fractions determined by Aalborg Portland and through the pilot Vaisala probe. The pilot CO₂ probes are expectedly correct since it checked towards calibration gas. Additionally, the possibility of false air was also ruled out. The dissimilarity can either be a constant offset or a relative error.

An offset was calculated between the two sets of CO₂ probe measurements. There is a constant offset of $7.3 \pm 2.0\%$, with a coefficient of variation (CV) of 27.8%:

$$y_{\text{CO}_2, \text{stack}} - y_{\text{CO}_2, \text{unit}} = 0.073 \quad (2)$$

The probes were also tested for a relative difference. This was determined to be $1.49 \pm 0.15\%$, with a CV value of 9.74%.

$$\frac{y_{\text{CO}_2, \text{stack}}}{0.014868} = y_{\text{CO}_2, \text{corrected}} \quad (3)$$

It is concluded that the relative difference is the most accurate representation of the difference, based on the CV values. The results of the corrections to the stack CO₂ measurements are demonstrated in Fig. 8. The calculations of the ratio and the offset of the stack measurements are performed on the CO₂ measured at the stack and plotted along with the CO₂ measured by the Vaisala probe in the pilot, in order to achieve a more accurate representation of the inlet gas.

3.2.3. Inlet gas composition

An example of the flue gas composition provided to the carbon capture unit over a month of operation, as provided from by Aalborg

Portland, is shown in Fig. 9. The concentration of CO₂, O₂, and H₂O is kept relatively steady throughout the whole month of operation, as illustrated in Fig. 9a. Monitoring the oxygen concentration is crucial as it has a role in oxidative degradation of the solvent. The flue gas, measured by Aalborg Portland, consists of approximately 35 vol% H₂O, 9 vol% O₂ and 22 vol% CO₂, upstream to passing through the gas cooler and entering the MTU.

After applying the offset and relative difference calculation there was a good match between the two data sources (Fig. 9).

The flue gas entering the plant consists of approximately 17 vol% CO₂ (after the correction). The measurements demonstrate that CO₂ and H₂O have a tendency follow a similar pattern of variation in concentration, where O₂ presents to have the opposite behavior.

Approximately 6.5 vol% of O₂, 7 mg/m³ of SO₂, and 400 mg/m³ of NO_x are present in the flue gas. NO and NO₂ are typically reported together as NO_x in emission monitoring of industrial flue gases, which is also the case for this study. O₂, NO_x, and SO₂ can lead to solvent degradation by reacting with the amine solvent and producing degradation products like amine salts, nitrosamines, and nitramines [9,51–54].

Overall, aside from the frequent fluctuations in CO levels, the other measured components maintain a relatively steady value, with only occasional peaks observed, as shown in Fig. 9. Constant observation of impurities, particularly those that can lead to solvent degradation, and the surveillance of potential spikes are crucial for monitoring solvent degradation and maintaining efficient operation of the carbon capture plant.

Fig. 8. Stack and MTUs probe raw CO₂ measurements, overlapping with the offset and the ratio corrections.

Fig. 9. Flue gas concentration of kiln 87 for a month of operation, as provided by Aalborg Portland. a) The concentration of H₂O, O₂, CO₂ (stack from AP), and two types of CO₂ corrections in (%), b) SO₂, c) CO, d) NO_x, e) NH₃, f) TOC, g) HCl in mg/Nm³ (left y-axis), and Hg in µg/Nm³ (right y-axis).

3.3. Emission measurements under base case conditions

To evaluate the effectiveness of a water bed and acid bed wash system, gas emission measurements were performed at various points in the system. Measurements were conducted before (GS2, Fig. 4) and after the wash tower (GS3, Fig. 4), followed by an assessment of the CO₂ gas stream exiting the desorber (GS4, Fig. 4). The streams were analyzed for flue gas derived compounds as well as amine related emissions.

The concentration of emission species in the gas stream that exits the plant was investigated to assess the environmental effect of the amine-operated capture unit. The emission species are divided into six sub-groups: 1) solvent amines, 2) alkylamines, 3) amides, 4) nitrosamines, 5) solvent-specific degradation products, and 6) nitramines.

Solvent amines refer to a blend of AMP and PZ. Alkylamines are amines in which the hydrogen atoms are replaced by alkyl or aryl groups. Alkylamines are formed due to carbamate polymerization at high temperatures [51]. Short-chained alkylamines are formed due to the degradation of amines. Amides are derived from carboxylic acids, where the hydroxyl group is replaced by an amine, e.g., acetamide (CH₃CONH₂). The formation of nitrosamines and nitramines is due to the reaction between the amines (AMP and PZ) and NO_x. High NO_x concentrations have been observed to cause higher nitrosamine and nitramine concentrations in the solvent for amines [33,46,55,56]. Finally, solvent-specific degradation products are byproducts that originate specifically from the degradation of this particular solvent and not all amines, e.g., AMPAMP (2-[(2-amino-2-methylpropyl)amino]-2-methyl-1-propanol).

The measurements of these components are discussed below in the context of operating the pilot in base case configuration. The inlet gas flow rate for this set of experiments is 130 kg/h.

3.3.1. Flue gas-derived components and smaller solvent degradation components

The fundamental smaller impurity molecules in the flue gas are composed of CO₂, CO, NO, NO₂, SO₂, NH₃, and HCl. The results of these components in the depleted flue gas and in the CO₂-rich stream are presented in Table 5, and discussed in detail below.

NO_x, SO_x, and HCl tend to react with amine solvents and produce degradation products like amine salts, nitrosamines, and nitramines, among others [9,51,52]. The temperatures of the stripper column can accelerate these reactions. Besides solvent degradation, HCl would likely cause damage to the carbon capture plant as it tends to be corrosive to stainless steel [57]. To prevent HCl in the flue gas from entering the system, the MTU is equipped with an activated carbon filter in the inlet stream (Fig. 2).

The high concentration of NO_x originates from the flue gas, as shown in Fig. 9e. Throughout the campaign, an average of 400 ± 100 mg/Nm³ was measured [43]. As shown in Table 5, NO_x was found at non-detectable levels in the CO₂ stream, indicating that most NO_x escapes with the depleted gas. In this work, gas sampling was performed at one location at a time. The discrepancies in the flue gas related compounds can be attributed to the fluctuations of the gas. In particular, the inconsistencies in CO and NO_x levels are likely due to changes in flue gas composition, as the carbon capture plant should have little to no

Table 5

Concentration of different components in all gas streams as measured by FORCE Technology. The sampling point is GS2-4, indicated in Fig. 4. Measurements are presented for experimental campaign combining acid and water wash.

	Unit	Before Wash Tower (GS2)	After Wash Tower (GS3)	Product Gas (GS4)
Date		29-08-2023	30-08-2023	30-08-2023
Time		16:06–17:06	09:44–10:44	12:16–13:16
Operating parameters				
CO ₂	% (d)	4.23	2.50	33.61w*
O ₂	% (d)	8.05	9.67	<0.21
Concentrations				
CO	mg/ m ³ (s, d)	674.23	133.76	<10.12
NO	mg/ m ³ (s, d)	327.37	364.65	<2.91
NO _x (calculated as NO ₂)	mg/ m ³ (s, d)	512.70	570.26	<4.47
HCl	mg/ m ³ (s, d)	<0.21	<0.21	<0.21
SO ₂	mg/ m ³ (s, d)	21.38	18.64	18.95
NH ₃	mg/ m ³ (s, d)	13.03	0.60	1.05
Formaldehyde	mg/ m ³ (s, d)	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Acetaldehyde	mg/ m ³ (s, d)	0.16	2.79	1.25
Acetone	mg/ m ³ (s, d)	1.71	1.30	4.98

(s,d) indicates dry and standard conditions (0 °C and 1013 hPa), < indicates below equipment detection level. *indicates equipment limitation; the upper limit is reached in the reach CO₂ stream. The gas is expected to be almost pure CO₂.

(†) A detailed description of the analytical methods used can be found in section 2.9.2.1 and 2.9.2.2.

influence on these compounds.

For all gas flows (GS2-4, Fig. 4), SO₂ was measured at similar levels. However, no SO₂ was detected in the inlet stream at the time of sampling for either stream. The detected SO₂ could have been the result of its release from the system, in the form of SO₂ rich aerosols. The aerosols likely originate from previous operation at higher sulfur concentration, which could have impacted the solvent. The constant level of SO₂ across all gas flows could also be related to equipment calibration drift or instrument inaccuracies, highlighting the importance of regular calibration, even in short-term sampling periods.

Ammonia can be formed due to amine degradation. The observed low concentration of ammonia correlates with low level of amine degradation [9,17,47]. Due to its high volatility, ammonia tends to escape the system with the depleted gas stream. Generally, the CESARI solvent has less emissions than MEA, as both AMP and PZ have higher oxidation stability than MEA [17]. Therefore, lower ammonia emissions could be expected in CESARI-operated carbon capture units. Still, ammonia can be considered one of the dominant oxidative degradation products for both AMP and PZ [18].

Oxidative degradation of amine solutions, mostly MEA, can lead to the formation of byproducts like acetaldehyde, formaldehyde, and acetone [22,58]. These compounds are usually present in the degradation of AMP/PZ solvent blends but in much lower levels [59,60]. In this work, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, and acetone were also measured in GS2 to GS4. Acetaldehyde and acetone were present in all measured gas

streams, suggesting that these compounds escape the system from all columns. Additionally, the measurements indicate that the acid wash had little to no effect in removing these compounds.

3.3.2. Amine degradation gas measurements in the depleted stream

Gas emission measurements before (GS2, Fig. 4) and after the wash tower (GS3) were compared, to evaluate the effectiveness of combining the water and acid wash in reducing emissions of degradation compounds. However, during the sampling process, aerosols containing amines may have escaped the system, potentially leading to elevated readings for some emissions.

0.1 M sulfuric acid circulated in the acid bed (Fig. 3), while the water wash operated to maintain the plant's water balance. In this work, we consider that it had little to no influence on the emissions, as the plant had been operating for an extended period of time, and the water was saturated by emission impurities

The wash tower, utilizing the acid loop, proved effective in reducing almost all emission compounds, as shown in Table 6. In particular, AMP decreases by a factor of 92.4%, from 182.6 to 13.8 mg/m³, and PZ by a factor of 94.2%, from 1.33 to 0.08 mg/m³, after passing through the wash column. Although significantly lower, the value for both –especially AMP–remains higher than expected for a double wash system, which could be explained by the possible presence of aerosols in the gas stream. The large amount of particularly AMP in the gas phase also reflects the decrease of liquid solvent wt%, which was observed to decrease throughout the months of operation.

The emission of alkylamines ranges from 15 to 285 µg/m³ before the wash tower, Table 6. All the compounds in the alkylamine subgroup show a reduction ranging from 77.1 to 99.5%. Ethylamine shows the most significant reduction from 284.8 to 1.5 µg/m³. After the wash tower, the concentration of ethylmethylamine is non-detectable.

Amides, nitramines, and most nitrosamines were non-detectable at equipment levels after the wash tower, as seen in Table 6. Two nitrosamines were present in the stream entering the wash tower. These were N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA), measured at 5.6 µg/m³, and N-Methylethanolamine (NMEA), measured at 0.19 µg/m³ (Table 6). NDMA was reduced by 79% and was measured to be 1.2 µg/m³ in the column outlet stream, while NMEA was below the detection limit.

Finally, solvent-specific degradation products were detected, with most appearing in both streams (GS2 and GS3). PZ-related compounds such as 4,4-dimethylpiperazine (DMO), MNPZ, and DNPZ are detected at the inlet stream of the column (GS2) in ranges from 11.1 to 93.0 µg/m³, with 2-oxopiperazine (2-OMP) measured below the detection limit in both streams. At the outlet stream, the PZ-related compounds show a reduction ranging from 18.5 to 86.6%, with MNPZ being reduced the least, from 93.0 to 75.7 µg/m³.

AMP-related compounds (Table 6) such as 2-[(2-amino-2-methylpropyl)amino]-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMPAMP), 2-methyl-2-(methylamino)-1-propanol (Methyl-AMP) and N-methyl-nitroso-amino-methylpropanol (Nitroso-methyl-AMP) are detected in the wash tower inlet stream, with methyl-AMP composing 99.7% of the three and 95.8% of the AMP-related compounds. Methyl-AMP is found to be 3.75 mg/m³ in the GS2 stream and is reduced to 0.32 mg/m³ in the outlet. AMPAMP was not detected in both streams. Nitroso-methyl-AMP showed an increase of 10.6 µg/m³. This result could suggest that the acid wash had little to no effect on this compound.

Overall, the acid wash reduces solvent emissions by 92.5% (from GS2 to GS3). The degradation product was reduced by 91.5% (from GS2 to GS3), with several compounds reaching non-detectable levels. A 92.4% overall reduction in emissions was achieved, highlighting the effectiveness of the wash tower in reducing amine-related compounds.

3.3.3. Amine degradation gas measurements in the CO₂ stream

The CO₂ gas stream exiting the desorber (Table 6, GS4) was measured and assessed for amine byproducts. The presence of impurities in the CO₂ product stream may impact the CO₂ infrastructure, e.g., CO₂

Table 6

Concentration of contaminants in the gaseous phase is measured by FORCE Technology (†). The sampling points, GS2-4, are indicated in Fig. 4. Measurements are presented for experimental campaign combining acid and water wash.

	Unit	Before Wash Tower (GS2)*	After Wash Tower (GS3)*	CO ₂ stream (GS4)*
Date		29–08-2023	30–08-2023	30–08-2023
Gas Volume	L/ sample	113.6	107.7	98.4
Solvent				
Amines				
AMP	mg/m ³ (s,d)	182.6	13.8	3.43
Piperazine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	1.33	0.0771	0.06
Alkylamines				
Methyl-amine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.254	0.0061	0.0051
Dimethyl-amine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.015	0.0008	0.0016
Ethyl-amine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.285	0.0015	<0.00049
Diethyl-amine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.0066	0.0015	<0.00049
Ethylmethyl-amine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.00125	<0.00037	<0.00049
Amides				
Formamide	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00023	<0.00019	<0.00025
Acetamide	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00023	<0.00019	0.0538
Nitroso-mix				
NDELA	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00012	<0.00009	<0.00012
NDMA	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.0056	0.0012	0.00086
NMOR	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00023	<0.00019	<0.00025
NMEA	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.00018	<0.00009	<0.00012
NPYR	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00012	<0.00009	<0.00012
NDEA	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00012	<0.00009	<0.00012
NPIP	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00012	<0.00009	<0.00012
NDPA	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00012	<0.00009	<0.00012
NDBA	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00012	<0.00009	<0.00012
Solvent specific degradation products				
DMO	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.0111	0.00149	0.03196
2-OXP	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00023	<0.00019	<0.00025
AMPAMP	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00023	<0.00019	<0.00025
methyl-AMP	mg/m ³ (s,d)	3.75	0.325	0.094
Nitroso-methyl-AMP	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.0095	0.02	0.0012
MNPZ	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.093	0.076	0.012
DNPz	mg/m ³ (s,d)	0.051	0.033	<0.00246
Nitramines				
MA-nitramine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00023	<0.00186	<0.00246
DMA-Nitramine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00023	<0.00186	<0.00246
AMP-nitramine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00023	<0.00019	<0.00025
Pz-nitramine	mg/m ³ (s,d)	<0.00023	<0.00186	<0.00246

(s,d) indicates dry and standard conditions (0 °C and 1013 hPa), *: "<" indicates below equipment detection level.

(†) A detailed description of the analytical methods used can be found in section 2.9.2.3.

transportation pipeline and ship transportation. In addition, byproducts in the CO₂ can affect the efficiency and effectiveness of a potential downstream CO₂ utilization. The impure CO₂ will influence various factors such as the range of operation, corrosion control, fluid density, and the total volume of CO₂ that can be transported, among others [57].

Although most degradation compounds are released from the absorber, a small amount still exits with the CO₂ stream, with solvent amines making up the largest share of these measured emissions. In particular, for the solvent amines, 3.43 and 0.06 mg/m³ of AMP and PZ were measured at GS4, respectively. Two alkylamines were detected in the CO₂ stream, methylamine at 5.0 µg/m³ and dimethylamine at 1.57 µg/m³, with the remaining species being below the detection limit.

In GS4, like the depleted gas streams (GS2 and GS3), most nitrosamines were non-detectable in the CO₂ product stream, with only NDMA being measured at 0.86 µg/m³. Unlike the previous gas streams, acetamide was detected in the stream, measured at 54.0 µg/m³.

Solvent-specific degradation products were detected. Methyl-AMP, which composed a large percentage of the degradation compounds in the absorber exhaust stream, was measured at 94.4 µg/m³. Nitroso-methyl-AMP was also measured at similar levels, while AMPAMP was not detected. PZ-related compounds, such as DMO and MNPZ, were measured at 32.0 µg/m³ and 11.8 µg/m³. 2-OXP and DNPz were not detected.

No nitramines were detected above the analytical detection limit in any of the sampled streams during this work. This finding supports the application of CESAR1 as a solvent, with minimal harmful effects, given that in vitro studies have demonstrated the potential carcinogenic and mutagenic properties of nitramines [61].

This work revealed that solvent amines were the most significant components across all gas streams, with AMP making up 92.9% of the CO₂ stream impurities. Additionally, AMP accounted for 96.9 and 96.2% of the gas streams exiting the absorber and in the depleted stream, respectively.

3.4. Double water wash test

To investigate the effect of water on emission removal, we introduce an additional water bed to the wash tower (Fig. 2). Additional water washing may reduce emissions since most amine degradation byproducts are water-soluble.

The ammonia concentration can be used as a critical indicator of solvent degradation, particularly in MEA-operated systems, where the presence of ammonia is an accepted assumption of degradation [9,47]. Our work assumes that CESAR1 follows the same tendency, though lower ammonia emission is expected [17,30]. In this study, ammonia levels are anticipated to be on the higher end compared to most AMP/PZ systems due to its presence in the flue gas. Although important, Moser et al. [30] demonstrated that aerosol levels have little to no impact on ammonia concentrations exiting the plant and therefore, they will not be a focus of further analysis in these tests. An FTIR analyzer (atmosFIR, Protea Ltd.) was used to measure ammonia concentration, providing insights into amine degradation.

A test was performed for which two water wash sections were used. The pilot only has one water wash section. To test two water wash sections, the acid wash is used as a water wash by draining out the acid and refilling it with demineralized water. The inlet gas flow rate for this test was 130 kg/h.

Initially, the second wash was kept dry to determine the base case of one water wash. This is shown for the time interval before the dotted blue line in Fig. 10 (up to 13:35). After that, demineralized water was pumped through the second bed. The liquid flow was gradually increased until the bed was sufficiently wet, as illustrated in Fig. 10, in the interval between blue and green dotted lines (13:37 to 14:14). At

Fig. 10. Ammonia concentration of the gas exiting the wash tower during water-to-water wash experiments (left y-axis), including the temperature of the upper two wash tower beds at the time of the measurement (right y-axis).

14:14, the flow rate was abruptly increased from 50 to 100 kg/h. At 14:20, the emissions increased, and the water flow was further increased to 150 kg/h, expecting an impact on emission reduction. However, emissions continued to rise until the end of the measurement period.

The increase in ammonia emissions, despite the water flow, can be explained by the solubility characteristics of ammonia. While ammonia is highly soluble in water, as with any gas, its solubility in water decreases as the temperature increases [62]. As illustrated in Fig. 10, the temperature at the top two beds of the wash tower – wash bed 4 (the acid bed) and wash bed 5 (the top dry bed) – initially dropped, as fresh water was introduced to the bed and it started increasing after about 40 min of circulation, at approximately 14:20. That is a result of the cooling of the wash tower decreasing. A similar trend can be observed by the ammonia emissions, which also began to increase at the same time.

Conclusively, the results indicate that although the water could reduce the ammonia levels by a few ppm, water alone was not enough to remove it under certain thermal conditions. The temperature dependency of ammonia makes water less than optimal for use as a scrubber for ammonia or amine byproducts in general, as increase of reduces solubility, directly impacting mass transfer efficiency. Additionally, the unit's outdoor location makes it susceptible to ambient temperature, which could directly affect the wash tower's effectiveness in removing degradation compounds. That would suggest that, while the double water wash effectively reduces ammonia emissions by a few ppm, further treatment may be necessary for more effective removal.

3.5. Influence of intercooling on emissions

3.5.1. Intercooler impact on the absorber temperature profile

The intercooling (IC) configuration enhances CO₂ absorption by cooling the solvent in a chosen absorber bed. The MTU allows changing

intercooler positions between bed intersections, either between top and middle or middle and bottom (Fig. 2). CO₂ absorption in amine solvents is an exothermic process [63,64], with the highest absorption usually occurring in the middle to upper section of the column. As a result, the intercooler is primarily required in the second bed of the absorber column to manage the generated heat of absorption. For the duration of the tests, the lean solvent that entered from the top of the absorber column had a temperature of 30.2 °C ± 1.7 °C.

The effect of the intercooler on the absorber temperature profile is instantaneous, as illustrated in Fig. 11a. This is indicated by the fast drop in temperatures of the whole column at 8:08, indicated by a vertical black line. The temperature drop is expectedly steep on the bed where the intercooler is installed, as illustrated in Fig. 11b, at approximately 10 m height from the column bottom.

Generally, by implementing the IC, the temperature of the absorber can decrease significantly, depending on the IC position and external temperatures, therefore enhancing CO₂ absorption. Additionally, intercooling has a major impact on wash tower performance and emission, as discussed below.

3.5.1.1. Intercooling's impact on wash column temperature. As mentioned above, the wash tower temperature is controlled by adjusting the cooling water flow to maintain the plant's water balance.

As illustrated in Fig. 12a, when a Motor Operated Valve (MOV) actively increases the cooling water flow, it is called "cooling on." Once the MOV reaches a position that maintains sufficient cooling to keep the absorber level steady, this condition is called "steady cooling."

The effect of the IC on the wash column temperature profile is instantaneous, as illustrated in Fig. 12a. This is evident by the temperature drop in the whole column at 8:08, marked by the vertical black line. However, the total effect is not apparent, as the column began

Fig. 11. a) raw transient data of the absorber temperature profile before and after turning on the intercooler. b) the temperature profile of the absorber in regard to height before and after the intercooler was turned on.

cooling shortly after, indicated by the dark blue color in Fig. 12a. The cooling water flow continued to increase for 44 min to keep the water balance in check, and the cooling continued to be active, as shown by the transition to light blue. Fig. 12a and Fig. 12b show the change in the temperature profile of the wash tower with and without the use of intercooling and cooling water.

The difference in the temperature profile of the wash tower is crucial, as fluctuations in temperature in the wash tower can significantly affect emissions [31,32].

3.5.1.2. Impact of intercooling on emissions. The impact of the intercooler on the emissions was investigated by first establishing a base case operation for the capture plant. Under base case conditions, the emissions exiting the absorber were measured (GS2, Fig. 4) using an FTIR. Like the previous tests, ammonia concentration was a key indicator of solvent degradation. For these experiments, the inlet gas flow rate were kept at 100 kg/h.

During the following tests, to investigate the effectiveness of the acid, the flow was gradually increased, as shown in Fig. 13 by the vertical lines. The lines represent a change in acid flow; the blue lines indicate a flow of 50 kg/h, green indicates 100 kg/h, pink indicates 150 kg/h, red indicates 200 kg/h, and black indicates 0 kg/h. The black horizontal lines on each plot represent the average ammonia emissions measured at GS2 (absorber outlet) for each experiment.

After the base case measurements, the plant stopped for a few hours due to an electrical malfunction. The plant operated for 3 h, after which measurements of the depleted flue gas exiting the absorber were conducted. The ammonia emissions measured at GS2 were much lower compared to the base case experiments, as shown in Fig. 13a (Acid-IC-Cold, Fig. 13), indicating less solvent degradation. Specifically, in the

base case, an average of 16.7 ppm of NH_3 was measured, while an average of 1.6 ppm of NH_3 was measured, exiting the absorber while the IC was on.

The emissions exiting the wash tower were also measured, while the acid flow gradually increased. The emission levels reached less than one ppm of ammonia after approximately 60 min of measuring and reached non-detectable levels after approximately 180 min of measuring, as illustrated in Fig. 13d. The effectiveness of the acid wash in reducing NH_3 levels aligns with expectations and is well-supported by existing literature [35,37,47]. Khakharia et al. [35] found that incorporating an acid wash section offers a simple and effective approach to reduce ammonia emissions in post-combustion CO_2 capture systems. Supporting the conclusion that an acid wash can successfully sustain emission reduction.

To further test the effect of IC on emissions, the plant was switching from base case to IC. The emission reduction can be reached without acid usage, as shown in Fig. 13a. To further reduce emissions in addition to IC, the acid proved to be very effective in reducing the ammonia emissions. The acid loop was turned off after approximately 73 mins of operation, to see if that would have any effect, as illustrated in Fig. 13e. After approximately 50 mins the ammonia levels began to increase, indicating that the bed had dried from any acid. The acid pump was turned on again 78 min after it was turned off. The emission entering the wash tower were reduced to non-detectable levels after 220 min of operation, as shown in Fig. 13e.

Overall, it was observed that the acid wash was highly effective in reducing ammonia levels and that the intercooler significantly influenced the amount of degradation products formed. These results align with the findings of Liu et al. [31], who observed a reduction in total amine emissions both before and after the implementation of control

Fig. 12. A): raw transient data of the wash column temperature profile. b) the temperature profile of the wash tower.

measures when intercooling was used. As shown in Fig. 13a, in the first test (water), where the pilot plant was operating in base case, an average of 11.7 ppm of NH_3 was measured exiting the absorber for 79 mins of measurement, with a maximum value of 27 ppm. In the base case test (Acid), an average of 16.7 ppm of NH_3 for 135 mins of measurement, with a maximum value of 25 ppm. For the intercooler tests, an average of 1.6 ppm of NH_3 with a maximum value of 4 ppm was measured for 103 mins for the third test (Acid-IC-Cold). Finally, after 142 mins of measurements, an average of 1.4 ppm of ammonia was measured with a max value of 4 ppm for the fourth test (Acid-IC). However, investigating a possible shift of emissions from the depleted to the CO_2 rich gas, when the intercooler is deployed would be of interest for future testing.

4. Conclusion

This work presents the effectiveness of implementing a wash tower, comprising of a conventional water wash and an acid wash section in reducing AMP/PZ degradation product content in the treated gas stream of a post-combustion carbon capture plant. The analysis revealed that, overall, there was a 92.4% reduction in all measured components following the wash tower, indicating a significant decrease in degradation products escaping the system.

By implementing the acid wash, AMP emissions decrease by a factor of 92.4%, from 182.6 to 13.8 mg/m^3 , and PZ emissions by a factor of 94.2%, from 1.33 to 0.077 mg/m^3 after passing through the wash column. Though significantly lower, the value for both is more than expected for a double wash system, which could be explained by the possible presence of aerosols in the gas stream.

The effect of introducing an additional water wash section was also investigated, with the results indicating that although the water could reduce the ammonia levels, it was not enough to remove it altogether. The temperature dependency of ammonia solubility makes water less than optimal for use as a scrubber for ammonia, and potentially other amine-derived byproducts, under certain thermal conditions in amine-

based carbon capture systems.

Furthermore, we show that absorber intercooling is an effective method for minimizing the emission of these amine byproduct compounds, with the results indicating that the intercooler significantly influenced ammonia emissions, and likely contributed to lowering the levels of other degradation products. However, further long-term testing should be conducted to investigate a possible shift of emissions from the depleted to the CO_2 -rich gas and reinforce the conclusions of this work.

These findings indicate that integrating an acid bed, while utilizing the intercooler, can mitigate degradation in amine-based solvents, thereby improving the efficiency and longevity of a thermal carbon capture plant.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT and Grammarly in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

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Fig. 13. a) the average ammonia emissions, for the different test conducted. b) ammonia concentration of the double water wash test, c) ammonia concentration of base case operation with acid wash, d) ammonia concentration of operation with ic on after stand-still and acid wash, e) ammonia concentration of operation with ic and acid wash.

& editing.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2025.133693>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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